

GLOBAL ANALYSIS OF ORIENTATION IN BMC AND RELATION WITH MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT : The fiber orientation is experimentally measured using image analysis. The goal of this study is to present the principle of this new method and recent results obtained for BMC composites. The method enables us to describe and to quantify the orientation of the reinforcement. First, we use microfocus X-ray technology to obtain gray level images. The contrast between the glass fibers and the matrix is good enough to visualize the flow pattern of the material. The image processing is based on the autocorrelation function. Results can be presented either as a table of values or as a polar diagram. Thanks to these quantitative data, we calculate an anisotropy rate, the fiber orientation parameter f_p and the orientation tensor. Results are correlated with mechanical properties. Three-point-bending and Charpy impact tests are performed in different locations and directions inside sheets moulded by compression and by injection processes.

KEYWORDS : Glass fiber composites, orientation, image analysis, autocorrelation, mechanical properties.

I - INTRODUCTION

BMC (or Bulk Molding Compounds) are polyester based thermoset compounds used in automotive and electrotechnology industries. They are more and more used because they offer a good set of properties especially thermomechanical performance. Properties depend on many structural parameters such as fiber-matrix interaction, fiber content, fiber aspect ratio, microvoids content and fiber orientation. It is well known that the flow of the material during the mold filling stage generates a complex fiber architecture. Parts often show a wide variation in their mechanical behavior. The dominant structural feature of fiber-reinforced composites is the arrangement of the fibers. The material properties and characteristics of the final parts are highly determined by the orientation. Thus, there is considerable interest in measuring and predicting the fiber orientation.

Many different methods have been developed to experimentally determine the fiber orientation. They can be divided into two categories :

- those, the most popular, which provide a detailed description of the orientation of each individual fiber. Images are generally carried out by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) or confocal microscopy [1] [2]. Then the microstructure is investigated by studying the elliptical shapes of the fibers' cross sections. These methods, based on binary images, are too local, especially for materials having a very large fiber-length distribution. These methods are time consuming because many fibers have to be measured for statistical reasons.

- those which are based on a global approach; they take the fiber–fiber interaction and their relative arrangement into account. They have the advantage of being faster and working with gray level images. Example of such methods includes Fraunhofer light diffraction. A complete theoretical analysis of the diffraction pattern is given by McGee and McGullough [3]. Denton *et al.* have shown that analysis of radiographic images by Fraunhofer light diffraction can provide a quantification of the degree of fiber orientation [4]. Moreover, Pourdeyhimi and Ramanathan developed a method based on the Fourier transform of the image, as spatial frequencies in a non-woven image are related to the orientation of the fibres [5].

The method based on the binarization of the X-ray images [6] is a kind of compromise.

For this reason, this paper presents a new technique, based on gray scale image analysis, which provides qualitative assessment and quantitative measurement of fiber orientation distribution and which can be applied to any fiber reinforced composite material.

Results of fiber orientation and mechanical property measurements for molded BMC composites are presented.

II - METHOD DEVELOPMENT

II-1. Principle

First, we present our method with idealized images of varying well known fiber distributions which are shown in figure 1.

Figure 1 : Simulated fiber distributions of 3 states of orientation (512 × 512 pixels images) and the corresponding autocorrelation images

The technique involves 2 steps. The first step consists of acquiring gray scale images. Initial images can be experimentally provided from non-destructive techniques like ultrasound (C-scan) or radiography.

The second step is analyzing the images. An own software has been developed [7]. The method is based on the autocorrelation function, a basic tool for signal analysis. The principle is to inspect the gray level image by performing all possible translations in all the directions. The stronger the alignment of reinforcement, the higher will be the values of the 2D autocorrelation function in this direction. Examples of this are given in figure 1. In each case, the central of the autocorrelation image

is the brightest part, it results from a summation of the principal trends contained in the initial image. Therefore, the autocorrelation image is symmetrical about its center.

The intensity of the autocorrelation obtained is counted, along a radius playing the role of an accumulator, for each angle between 0 and 179° (cf. figure 3). The values are then written into a result file.

In order to analyze orientation at different scales, we can adjust the accumulator's length. More precisely, the accumulator starts at the radius value R_1 , ends at the value R_2 (cf. figure 3) and it is corrected for the area covered by the way of a linear function decreasing from R_1 to R_2 [8].

Figure 2 : Definition of axis

Figure 3 : Scanning of the accumulator on the central part of the autocorrelation image

The values can be plotted on cartesian or polar graphs as “orientation roses”, as shown in figure 4. The raw result is called the absolute rose, and the values of the relative rose are those exceeding the minimum value of the “absolute” set.

Random fiber distribution results in circular orientation roses. As the degree of fiber orientation increases, the rose stretches out along the preferential direction of orientation.

cartesian representation of the relative values

polar representation : « relative rose »

Figure 4 : Two possible illustrations of the orientation for the distribution of the figure 1 where the fibers are transversally aligned

II-2. Quantitative parameters

Using the data provided by the previous analysis, the orientation can be represented by quantitative parameters.

First, we defined an anisotropy rate :

$$\text{anisotropy rate} = 100 \times \text{area of the relative rose} / \text{area of the absolute rose}$$

In the literature, many authors proposed quantitative descriptors. Among them, Advani and Tucker proposed a model that predicts the fiber-orientation distribution Ψ (FOD) [9]. We used this distribution function, defined such that the probability of the reinforcement will be placed between the angle Φ and $\Phi+d\Phi$. The function Ψ is symmetric, periodic and normalized on an interval of width π . The angle ϕ describes the orientation in the plane.

$$\int_0^{\pi} \Psi(x, y, \phi) \cdot \phi d\phi = 1$$

The second order orientation tensor components in the plane can be written as :

$$a_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} \langle \cos^2 \phi \rangle & \langle \sin \phi \cdot \cos \phi \rangle \\ \langle \sin \phi \cdot \cos \phi \rangle & \langle \sin^2 \phi \rangle \end{bmatrix}$$

The orientation tensor is a compact description of the fiber orientation state. Each component indicates the magnitude of the fibers alignment in the respective directions.

In the case of planar distribution of fibers, Hermans' orientation descriptor f_p is of the form :

$$f_p = 2\langle \cos^2 \phi \rangle - 1.$$

where the angle brackets denote an averaged quantity : $\langle \cos^2 \phi \rangle = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{179^\circ} N_i(\phi_i) \cos^2 \phi_i}{\sum_{i=0}^{179^\circ} N_i(\phi_i)}$

N_i is the stored relative value of the accumulator and ϕ_i corresponds to each associated angle, between 0 and 179°.

For composite materials where the fibers are randomly placed f_p is zero. If the fibers are aligned parallel to the direction 1, $f_p = 1$ and if the fibers are aligned perpendicular to direction 1, $f_p = -1$ (cf. figure 2).

The fibre orientation tensor has a principle moment A too. Dweib *et al.* use it to predict the effect of orientation on material properties [10].

$$A = 0.5 + \sqrt{(a_{11} - 0.5)^2 + a_{12}^2}$$

A is found to be 0.5 for random orientations and 1 for completely aligned fibers.

Furthermore, Krenchel has defined an orientation efficiency coefficient η [11] [12]. This factor η is determined both in longitudinal and in the transverse directions.

$$\eta_{0T} = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{179^\circ} N_i \cos^4 \phi_i}{\sum_{i=0}^{179^\circ} N_i} \quad \text{and} \quad \eta_{0L} = \frac{\sum N_i \cos^4(\phi_i + 90^\circ)}{\sum N_i}$$

It corresponds to a fiber orientation correction and might be incorporated in mechanical models. It takes its origin in the models for unidirectional composites. When reinforcement is parallel to applied load : $\eta_0 = 1$, whereas when reinforcement is perpendicular to applied load : $\eta_0 = 0$.

Note that values of η_{0L} , η_{0T} , a_{11} and a_{22} are weighted by the anisotropy rate.

The degree of fiber orientation can vary from random to totally aligned. Usually, throughout the molded part, the orientation state is between these two extremes.

Accuracy of the method is verified using generated images with known characteristics. This preliminary study of model images allows us to say there is a good correlation between theoretical and measured parameters.

	value	Anisotropy rate (%)	f_p	a_{11}	a_{12}	a_{22}	A	η_{0L}	η_{0T}
Random distribution	theoretical	0	0	0,5	0	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
	measured	5.4	-0.02	0.49	0	0.51	0.51	0.348	0.367
Fibers aligned in direction 1	theoretical	100	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
	measured	94.1	0.88	0.98	0	0.02	0.98	0.01	0.834
Fibers aligned in direction 2	theoretical	100	-1	0	0	1	1	1	0
	measured	95.3	-0.86	0.13	-0.01	0.87	0.86	0.849	0.036

Table 1 : Quantitative parameters of idealized images of figure 1

III - APPLICATION

Based on the above results, we can now work on real images.

Bulk Molding Compound (BMC) is a fiber-reinforced thermoset composite consisting of chopped E-glass strands and particulate fillers (like calcium carbonate). Initially, the fiberglass strands were 6 and 4.5 mm long and were randomly distributed before processing. BMC with 20 % by weight of glass fiber was molded by compression and injection into flat rectangular plaques measuring respectively 170 mm×170 mm×30 mm and 300 mm×120 mm×3 mm.

In contrast to the behavior seen in reinforced thermoplastic moldings, fiber orientation does not vary significantly through the thickness of moldings. As the tool surface is hotter than the compound, plug flow velocity profile takes place across the thickness of the sheets [13]. We assume that fiber orientation does not vary significantly through the thickness. Consequently, the orientation is considered as two-dimensional.

Radiography is non-destructive and allows glass fibers to be seen through the entire thickness of a molded part. The reinforcement appears like dark areas in X-ray and the resin like brighter areas. A microfocus target with 35 kV voltage and 400 mA tube current is used to produce radiographs of the sheets.

Figure 5 : Examples of X-radiographs (34×34 mm) of compression (a) and injection (b) (c) molded BMC plaques with a thickness of 3 mm (20 % by weight of fibreglass)

Images are acquired with a radiographic digital X-ray imager consisting of amorphous silicon sensors that are able to correct the illumination variations of the X source in order to give “flat” images [14]. Images acquired with a 12-bit scales are converted into 8-bit ones. So, gray level images contain 256 steps between black (0) and white (255).

In order to get a good estimate of the fiber orientation distribution we need fairly large images. Attention was devoted to examining the location of the fracture surface of the different tested samples. We have chosen 1024×1024 pixels that is to say 34×34 mm images, because this size encompasses the wide variety of failure zones. Otherwise, we varied the length of the accumulator from 0.5 mm to 15 mm. We examined the fracture surface and 15 mm corresponds to the furthest distance from the middle point of the sample where we detected the crack after mechanical testing.

The mechanical properties of compression and injection molded plaques were investigated by three point bending and Charpy impact tests. They were performed at room temperature in accordance to the ISO 179 standard for the Charpy impact test. For the flexural test, samples of dimensions 9 mm×5 mm×3 mm have been cut. To obtain consistent values, it was necessary to test 50 samples for each test.

In the injection process case, the anisotropy is taken into account by taking samples in directions parallel and perpendicular to the major direction of orientation (direction2). The results are reported in table 2 and the anisotropy effects illustrated in figure 6 by using transverse / longitudinal ratios. The longitudinal direction or direction 2 is the one of preferential alignment of the fibers after injection molding.

		BMC with 6 mm long fibers molded by injection	BMC with 4.5 mm long fibers molded by injection	BMC with 4.5 mm long fibers molded by compression
FLEXURAL MODULUS (MPa)	direction 1	9209 (0,7%)	8547 (3,9%)	8336 (3%)
	direction 2	8345 (0,6%)	8550 (5,3%)	
FLEXURAL STENGTH (MPa)	direction 1	64,5 (1,6%)	62,59 (12%)	95.8 (12%)
	direction 2	68,4 (2,7%)	92,92 (9,4%)	
CHARPY IMPACT STRENGTH (kJ/m2)	direction 1	5,8 (38,3%)	6,75 (22%)	40.72 (24%)
	direction 2	14 (42%)	21,08 (7,2%)	

Table 2 : Mechanical property results for BMC sheets (20% by weight fiber content). The first values correspond to an average(m) of 50 experiments and the second to the variation coefficient ($\sigma/m \times 100$).

In the compression molding case, the random fiber architecture gives, as expected, values close to 1 for orientation parameters ratios, that is to say the material is isotropic.

Injection molding is very widely used. A major advantage of this manufacturing technique may be found in the capacity of forming fairly complex shapes at high production rate. Nevertheless, the process induces fiber orientation effects, which are probably the largest factor causing strength variations in parts [15]. Fiber alignment is beneficial for properties in the alignment direction but deteriorious in perpendicular direction. In our case, the divergent flow that takes place in the gate region leads to fiber orientation in the direction transverse to the direction of injection.

Measured values reflect the degree of anisotropy. Especially, strong differences in flexural and impact strength between the two directions are clearly noticed.

It has also to be noticed that the orientation parameter ratios η_{0T} / η_{0L} and a_{11} / a_{22} show a very similar behaviour.

(a) BMC with 6 mm long-fibers injected

(b) BMC with 4.5 mm long-fibers injected

(c) BMC with 4.5 mm long-fibers compressed

Figure 6 : Mechanical properties related to quantitative orientation results
 (The orientation values were weighted by the anisotropy rate)
 Longitudinal direction or direction 2 is the one of preferential fibers alignment

As the whole thickness of the sheet is taken into account for image analysis, a scale shorter than 0.5 mm would not be significant. For the accumulator's lengths about 1 and 3 mm, the ratio values of the measured orientation parameters show an interesting tendency to be near of those of the Charpy impact tests. Actually, keeping in mind that the failure mechanism is multiscale, we had chosen to study orientation parameters along such a large scale.

Fiber orientation global parameters measured by radiography and image processing can be related to measured mechanical properties, especially connected to strength.

IV - ORIENTATION CARTOGRAPHY

Cartography consists of automatically dividing the initial image into smaller ones. It can be seen from figure 7 that one rose is generated for each sub-image. So, it is possible to obtain in the same image different local information at different scales, as the size of the sub images can be chosen.

Figure 7 : Fiber orientation distributions obtained by image processing

These experimental cartographies can be used to validate the numerical predictions of flow simulation softwares, following Kim *et Al* [16], by using a multiscale approach.

V - CONCLUSION

We describe a non-destructive technique which is a rapid and global method to determine the degree of fiber orientation. The results from these study indicate that our method is a powerful tool for characterizing qualitatively and quantitatively fiber orientation with a multiscale and multiresolution approach.

The theoretical and besides experimental results show that the developed tool for measuring fiber orientation is sufficiently accurate and thus suitable.

This technique are potentially useful for research on fiber orientation; development of prototype parts, optimization of molding conditions, validation of the orientation predictions of the simulation softwares and production quality control.

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